

126° (lit.¹⁴ 126–27°); hydrolysis afforded β -sitosterol, (I) γ -sitosterol, m.p. 145° (lit.¹⁵ 146°); acetate m.p. 142° (lit.¹⁶ 143°), (J) betulin, m.p. 249°; diacetate m.p. 215–16°; benzoate, m.p. 18–7° (K) friedelin, m.p. 260° (lit.¹⁷ 260–62°); benzoate 258–60°; (lit.¹⁸ 255–63°).

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to Prof. J. P. Tandon, Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur for facilities, and the Malaysian Embassy, New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. L. HARSH and H. C. BOHRA, Botany Study Centre, ICAR Publication No. 25, 1985, pp. 1–11.
2. H. THIEME and A. KHOGALI, *Pharmazie*, 1974, 29, 352.
3. I. HEILBORN and M. H. BUNBURY, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", Eyre and Spottiswoode, London, 1953, Vol. I, p. 445.
4. K. A. VESTERBURG and R. VESTERBURG, *Arkiv. Kem. Mineral Geol.*, 1926, 9, 17.
5. P. B. OELRICHS and T. MEYER, *Queensland J. Agric. Sci.*, 1962, 19, 1.
6. F. M. BAILEY, L. R. MURRAY, J. D. MCCONNELL and J. H. WITHELM, *Aust. J. Sci.*, 1964, 24, 41.
7. A. ZINCKE, A. FRIEDRICH and A. ROLLET, *Monatsch. Chem.*, 1920, 41, 253.
8. R. M. BERI and O. P. SHARMA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 501.
9. D. R. GUPTA and S. K. GARG, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 45, 250.
10. M. H. COHEN, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1907, 24, 236 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1908, 2, 1447).
11. I. HEILBORN and H. M. BUNBUSY, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", Eyre and Spottiswoode, London, 1953, Vol. I, p. 158.
12. E. LEVIN, V. K. COLLINS, D. S. VARNER and W. G. MOSOR, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1962, 57, 23516.
13. Y. TANAKE, K. OGURA, S. SAKAI and K. TANANISHI, *Yakugaku Zasshi*, 1964, 84, 887.
14. I. HEILBORN and H. M. BUNBUSY, "Dictionary of Organic Compound", Eyre and Spottiswoode, London, 1953, Vol. IV, p. 301.
15. K. SLOTTA and N. KAUS, *Chem. Ber.*, 1968, 17, 1991.
16. K. C. JOSHI and T. SHARMA, *Phytochemistry*, 1974, 13, 2010.
17. E. J. COREY and J. J. UPSPRUNG, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 3667.
18. N. L. DRAKE and R. P. JACOBSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1570.

Isolation of Kaempferol and Velutin from *Trifolium alexandrinum* (Leguminosae)

V. K. SAXENA* and A. K. JAIN

Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar-470 003

Manuscript received 12 February 1986, accepted 2 August 1986

COUMESTROL and phytoestrogens¹ have already been reported in *Trifolium alexandrinum*²; and since there are reports about the occurrence of

flavones in leguminosae species³, hence the *T. alexandrinum* was investigated for the presence of kaempferol and velutin.

Experimental

A 95% ethanolic extract of air-dried plant was successively extracted with non-polar to polar reagents. Water-soluble part of the ethyl acetate fraction gave two spots on tlc and then subjected to column chromatography to get the compounds A and B which gave the positive test for flavones⁴.

Compound-A: Yellow needles, m.p. 275–277° (Found: C, 62.84; H, 3.43. $C_{15}H_{10}O_6$ calculated for: C, 62.86; H, 3.48%); λ_{max} (MeOH) 264, 323, 361, + NaOMe 272, 320, 414 + $AlCl_3$ 260, 268, 308, 355, 429, + $AlCl_3/HCl$ 255, 270, 310, 350, 429 + NaOAc 275, 305, 360, + NaOAc/ H_3BO_3 264, 300, 328 and 380 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3580, 2915, 1680, 1590, 1440, 1260, 1130 and 825 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.12 (s, C_4 -OAc), 2.32 (s, C_7 -OAc), 2.40 (s, C_3 -OAc), 2.43 (s, C_5 -OAc), 6.72 (d, J 2.5 Hz C_6 -H), 7.35 (d, J 1.3 Hz, C_8 -H, C_8 -H) and 7.42 (d, J 7.8 Hz, C_6 -H); M^+ 286; m/e 285, 258, 153, 152, 134 and 124. Thus it was identified as 3,4',5,7-tetrahydroxyflavone (kaempferol),

Compound-B: M.p. 223–25° (Found: C, 64.98; H, 4.55. $C_{17}H_{14}O_6$ calcd. for: C, 64.93; H, 4.52%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 264, 350, + $AlCl_3$ 266, 385, + NaOEt 290 and 394 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3430, 2945, 2855, 1170, 1655, 1600 and 850 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 3.82 (s, C_7 -OMe), 3.90 (s, C_8 -OMe), 6.32 (d, J 2.5 Hz, C_6 -H), 6.70 (d, J 2.8 Hz, C_8 -H), 6.92 (s, C_5 -H), 2.43 (s, C_5 -OAc), 7.60 (dd, J 2.5, 8.5 Hz C_2 -H, C_6 -H), 2.13 (s, C_4 -OAc) and 7.1 (d, J 8.5 Hz, C_2 -H). Thus it was identified as 5,4'-dihydroxy-7,3'-dimethoxyflavone (velutin).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (A.K.J.) is thankful to I.C.M.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. H. MOHSIN and A. K. PAL, *Indian J. Antm. Sci.*, 197, 45, 622.
2. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYER and I. C. CHOPRA, "Supplement to Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1974, p. 97.
3. M. KANETA, H. HIKICHI, S. ENDO and N. SUGIYAMA, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1980, 44, 1407.
4. K. V. RAO and T. R. SESHADRI, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, 1948, 27, 375.